

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of some quinoline appended 1,2,3-triazoles

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Abstract : A series of 1,2,3-appended quinoline carboxylic acid derivatives were synthesized by pfitzinger reaction method using 1,2,3-triazole ketones and isatin. 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reaction between aromatic azide and acetylacetone yielded the triazole unit containing ketone functionality. The synthesized compounds were characterized by the usual spectral techniques to confirm the chemical structure. All the compounds were subjected to antimicrobial and antifungal studies against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigates*. The compounds show moderate to good biological activity.

Keywords : 1,2,3-Triazole, quinoline carboxylic acid, antibacterial activity, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

1,2,3-Triazole and its derivatives enhanced considerable attention for the past few decades due to their chemotherapeutic value¹. Quinoline and its derivatives are well known for their antimalarial and therapeutic properties. Quinoline alkaloids such as quinine, chloroquine, mefloquine and amodiaquine are used as efficient drugs for the treatment of malaria². The quinoline skeleton is often used for the design of many synthetic compounds with diverse pharmaceutical properties prompted by the above observations and as part of the general search for chemotherapeutically important nitrogen containing heterocycles^{3,4}. Chemotherapeutic activity of nitrogen heterocycles is almost always associated with compounds having the nitrogen containing group attached to C-5 of the five-membered heterocycle⁵ containing appropriate substituents at C-2 and C-5 of six membered heterocycle. These peptidomimetics that display protein-like functionality yet do not contain the labile amide linkage have wide-ranging potential as modulators of protein-protein interactions. Quinoline was chosen because it is small in size, biocompatible and easy to manipulate synthetically. In particular, substitutions at the second position of quinoline are known to have strong impact on their biological activities⁶. Similarly, the 1,2,3-triazole moiety is a potential pharmacophore owing to its moderate dipole char-

acter and rigidity, thereby used as a passive linker between two respective fragments of structural space⁷. Above pharmacological applications of the quinoline ring system has made driving force for increasing interest in the synthetic routes of quinoline containing triazole moiety. In the present work we made an attempt to combine the above pharmacophoric fragments in a single molecule. The quinoline triazole hybrid general structure is as follows :

Results and discussion

1,2,3-Triazole appended quinoline carboxylic acid derivatives were successfully synthesized from isatin and ketofunctionalized triazole derivative. The triazole compound were synthesized through 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of aromatic azides and 1,4-diketone under basic condition. The compound thus obtained was treated with isatin prepared by the literature method reported elsewhere under pfitzinger reaction conditions. The final compound thus

obtained was purified using column chromatography and further the purity was checked by HPLC method. The entire scheme of the synthesis of the compounds is given in the Fig. 1. Similarly procedure was adopted for synthesizing the all other compounds in the series showed in the Scheme 1. The compounds were subjected to anti

Antibacterial activity :

The newly synthesized compounds (**a-j**) were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli* (ATTC-25922), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATTC-25923), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATTC-27853), *Bacillus subtilis* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (recultured) bacterial stains

Fig. 1. Scheme of the synthesis of compounds **a-j**.

fungal and antimicrobial activity studies.

Antibacterial studies against various bacterial strains show mixed results but comparing with standard compound viz. nitrofurazone, these were shown good MIC values. Compound **e** shows no inhibition against *Escherichia coli* but with *Staphylococcus aureus*, it shows the MIC values less than the standard. Compound **d** shows very good inhibition against all the bacterial strains which is having fluorine at 4th position, but in the case of compound **g** where the same fluorine is at 2nd position shows only 12.5 as MIC values.

Antifungal studies against two fungal stains show moderate to good activity. The activity of the synthesized compounds was compared with standard Amphotericin B. As like in the case of antifungal compound **d** shows good inhibition values whereas the other compounds show poor inhibition.

by disc diffusion method^{8,9}. The discs measuring 6.25 mm in diameter were punched from Whatman No. 1 filter paper. Batches of 100 discs were dispensed to each screw capped bottles and sterilized by dry heat at 140 °C for an hour. The test compounds were prepared with different concentrations using dimethyl sulfoxide 1% (DMSO). One millilitre containing 100 times the amount of chemical required in each disc was added to each bottle which contains 100 discs. The discs of each concentration were placed in triplicate in nutrient agar medium seeded with fresh bacteria separately. The incubation was carried out at 37.8 °C for 24 h. Nitrofurazone was used as a standard drug. Solvent and growth controls were kept. The zone of inhibition and minimum inhibitory concentrations [MIC] was noted. The MIC values of tested compounds are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of **a-j** against standards

Code	Antibacterial				Antifungal	
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (Recultured)	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (Recultured)	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (Recultured)	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (Recultured)	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> (Recultured)	<i>Aspergillus fumigates</i> (Recultured)
a	25	12.5	6.25	12.5	6.25	12.5
b	12.5	12.5	6.25	6.25	NI	12.5
c	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	100
d	6.25	6.25	6.25	25	6.25	12.5
e	6.25	NI	100	12.5	12.5	12.5
f	6.25	12.5	NI	NI	12.5	12.5
g	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	NI
h	NI	6.25	12.5	6.25	12.5	12.5
i	12.5	25	25	25	NI	6.25
j	6.25	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
Nitrofurazone	<6.25	<6.25	<6.25	<6.25	-	-
Amphotericin B	-	-	-	-	<6.25	<6.25
DMSO (1%)	00	00	00	00	00	00

NI : No Inhibition.

Antifungal activity :

Antifungal activity for newly prepared compounds was screened by serial plate dilution method. Sabourands agar media was prepared by dissolving peptone (1 g), D-glucose (4 g) and agar (2 g) in distilled water (100 ml) and adjusting the pH to 5.7. Normal saline was used to make a suspension of spores of fungal strain for lawning. A loopful of particular fungal strain was transferred to 3 ml saline to get a suspension of corresponding species. A 20 ml of agar media was poured in to each of the petridishes. Excess of suspension was decanted and the plates were dried by placing in an incubator at 37 °C for 1 h. Using an agar punch wells were made on these seeded agar plates and 10 mg/ml of the test compounds in DMSO were added into each well labeled. A control was also prepared for the plates in the same way using solvent DMSO. The petridishes were prepared in triplicate and maintained at 37 °C for 3–4 days. Antifungal activity was determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone. Activity of each compound was compared with Amphotericin B as standard. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) for the Amphotericin B in DMSO was more than 1 mg/ml against the tested species. The MIC values of tested compounds are given in Table 1.

Experimental

1-(1-Phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)ethanone and isatin was synthesized as per the procedure reported in the literature (2).

*Synthesis of 2-(5-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)quinoline-4-carboxylic acid (a-j) :*

1-(1-Phenyl-1*H*-1,2,3-triazol-4-yl)ethanone (100 mmol) was dissolved in ethanol (20 ml). Isatin (100 mmol) was added in lot wise. The reaction mixture was stirred at 25–28 °C. Sodium hydroxide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in water (20 ml) and added dropwise to the reaction mixture and heated to reflux for 24 h (till completion of reaction). The mixture was cooled to room temperature and the solvent was evaporated using rotary evaporator. The residue obtained was dissolved in small amount of water and pH of the solution was adjusted to 3.5 using cooled dil. HCl. The precipitated solid was filtered and dried at 50 °C. The compound was further purified by column chromatography using cyclohexane and THF mixtures. Similarly other compounds in the series are prepared and characterized. Representative spectral data of the titled compound is presented here. For other compounds the spectral data are comply with the respective structural features.

IR KBr, cm^{-1} : 1697 (aryl C=O str.), 1239 (N-C str.), 1503 (Ar C=N); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) δ : 2.9 (3H, s, triazole CH_3), 14 (1H, s, COOH), 7.9–8.6 (Ar H); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , ppm) : δ 167 (COOH), 10 (triazole CH_3), 120–151 (Ar-C).

Conclusion

A series of quinoline carboxylic acid derivative using pfitzinger reaction synthesized from isatin and various 1,2,3-triazole containing keto functional group. Structures of the synthesized compounds were investigated by usual spectral techniques to ascertain the chemical structure. The purity of the compounds was analyzed by HPLC and purity was found to above 99.5%. Microbial screenings of the compounds reveal that these compounds are moderate to good activity compared to market available standards.

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